

Comparison Different Activation on Model Fit for Cats and Dogs Deep Learning CNN

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Abstract— Deep learning is a subset of machine learning, essentially a neural network with three or more layers. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning algorithm which can take in an input image, assign importance (learnable weights and biases) to various aspects/objects in the image and be able to differentiate one from the other. The general idea of this study is to see how the fake cats and dogs will affect the result of this CNN model and we also want to see the differences between each activation function used in model fit for cats vs dogs CNN in the training and validation loss and accuracy. softmax, sigmoid, and softplus for each epoch the value is unstable, but for the rest of function activation the result is close to 1 for accuracy and close to zero for the loss.

Keywords—Deep learning, CNN, Cat, Dog, Image, Function Activation

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning, essentially a neural network with three or more layers. These neural networks attempt to simulate the behavior of the human brain. While neural network with a single layer can still make approximate predictions, additional hidden layers can help to optimize and refine for accuracy [1]. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning algorithm which can take in an input image, assign importance (learnable weights and biases) to various aspects/objects in the image and be able to differentiate one from the other. The pre-processing required in a CNN is much lower as compared to other classification algorithms. While in primitive methods filter are hand-engineered, with enough training, CNN have the ability to learn these filters/characteristics. The architecture of a CNN is analogous to that of the connectivity pattern of Neurons in the Human Brain and was inspired by the organization of the Visual Cortex. Individual neurons respond to stimuli only in a restricted region of the visual field known as the Receptive Field. A collection of such fields overlaps to cover the entire visual area. [2].

For this experiment we will try to see the differences between each function activation in model fit. We also used fake cats and fake dogs in the test dataset. The result we will compare will be loss, validation loss, accuracy, validation accuracy.

Figure 1. Example of Cat and Dog used in Training and Validation Dataset

Figure 2. Example of Fake Cat and Dog used in Test Dataset

II. DATA PREPARATION

A. Data Source

Material used in this paper is the cats and dogs dataset that was given at the start of the simulation with an addition fake cats and dogs to become the data test to see whether the model can differentiate the real cat and dog with the fake one. The total data is divided into three categories: training dataset, test dataset, and validation dataset. The training dataset consist of 10.000 pictures of dogs and cats with the total of 20.000 pictures. the test dataset consists of 100 pictures of fake cats and dogs with the total of 200 pictures. The validation dataset consists of 1250 pictures of dogs and cats with the total of 1250 pictures. In figure 1 we can see the example of picture cat and dog respectively used in training and validation dataset, meanwhile in figure 2 we can see the example of the fake cat and dog picture respectively used in test dataset.

III. METHOD

A. General Idea

The general idea of this study is to see how the fake cats and dogs will affect the result of this CNN model and we also want to see the differences between each activation function used in model fit for cats vs dogs CNN in the training and validation loss and accuracy. There are relu, sigmoid, softmax, softplus, softsign, and selu method that will be compared.

To compare it we only need to change all the function activation in the model fit block. All of the activation will be changed but the last dense layer will stay the same using sigmoid activation function. We can see the selu function activation in Figure 3.

Building a Network

```

model = models.Sequential()

model.add(layers.Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='selu',\
input_shape=(150, 150, 3)))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(layers.Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='selu'))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(layers.Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='selu'))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(layers.Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='selu'))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D((2, 2)))
model.add(layers.Flatten())
model.add(layers.Dense(512, activation='selu'))
model.add(layers.Dense(1, activation='sigmoid'))
    
```

Figure 3. Selu Function Activation usage on model fit

IV. RESULT

After the model for all function activation was ran, we can see the differences of the result in the training and validation accuracy and training validation loss itself. Each model was trained with 40 epochs each. Table 1 shown is the last epoch loss, accuracy, validation loss, and validation accuracy and Figure 4 is the all the result in linechart. If we are only see the result from the table we will see that Selu have the best loss and accuracy, but softsign have the best validation loss and validation accuracy. From the figure we can see that softmax, sigmoid, and softplus for each epoch the value is unstable, but for the rest of function activation the result is close to 1 for accuracy and close to zero for the loss.

TABLE I. RESULT OF EACH FUNCTION ACTIVATION

Function Activation	Loss	Accuracy	Val_loss	Val_accuracy
Relu	0.3861	0.8220	0.3955	0.8190
Softmax	0.6932	0.5000	0.6933	0.4890
Sigmoid	0.6941	0.5090	0.6930	0.5090
Softplus	0.6955	0.5045	0.6926	0.4990
Softsign	0.3582	0.8415	0.3483	0.8330
Selu	0.2899	0.8815	0.4956	0.7800

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 4. Result of Different Function Activation (a) Relu, (b) Softmax, (c) Sigmoid, (d) Softplus, (e) Softsign, (f) Selu

V. CONCLUSION

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning, essentially a neural network with three or more layers. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning algorithm which can take in an input image, assign importance (learnable weights and biases) to various aspects/objects in the image and be able to differentiate one from the other. The general idea of this study is to see how the fake cats and dogs will affect the result of this CNN model and we also want to see the differences between each activation function used in model fit for cats vs dogs CNN in the training and validation loss and accuracy. softmax, sigmoid, and softplus for each epoch the value is unstable, but for the rest of function activation the result is close to 1 for accuracy and close to zero for the loss.

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